

Biofilm Formation and Antibiotic Profile of Bacteria Isolated from Urinary Tract Infections

Jenan M. Al-Aragi

Department of Biology College of Science, University of Basrah, Iraq

Wijdan H. Al-Tamimi

Department of Biology College of Science, University of Basrah, Iraq

Furdos Noori Jafer

Department of Biology College of Science, University of Basrah, Iraq

Abstract

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is a general term that refers to the presence of microorganisms in the urine. A total of 75 urine samples were collected. All samples were cultured, as suspected of having UTI, and 43 samples (57.3 %) showed growth (positive culture), while 32 samples (42.6 %) were negative cultures. Gram-negative bacteria were the predominant cause of UTI with percentage (93%). While gram-positive were found in 6.96%. *E.coli* were the predominant Gram-negative genus to isolate from UTI patients, while *Staphylococcus sp.* were the predominant among gram-positive bacteria. Isolation and identification of the bacteria based on traditional diagnostic tests such as Catalase, Oxidase, Coagulase tests and VITEK-2 system. The study involved determining the antibiotic susceptibility of isolates against 21 antibiotics, the results showed that all pathogens detected were resistant to at least 1-2 antibiotics. The antibiotic that showed highest sensitivity among antibiotics were Ciprofloxacin except *K.pneumoniae* and *S.haemolyticus*, *E.faecalis*. Meropenem antibiotic was more effective against all gram-negative Bacteria. Biofilm detection by using two different methods: Tube method (TM), Congo red agar method (CRA), among the total organisms isolated 25 (58.1%) showed Biofilm producer (BP), while 18 (41.8 %) Non Biofilm producer (NBP). Strong biofilm production was observed in *E.coli*, *P.aeruginosa*, *K.pneumoniae*. Most of uropathogens form biofilms, with a higher prevalence in antibiotic-resistant strains, sensitive bacteria also form biofilms but less frequently.

Introduction

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are among the most common infectious diseases in the world, impacting millions of people annually. Every part of the urinary system can become infected, including the kidneys (pyelonephritis), urethra (urethritis), and bladder (cystitis) [1]. A urinary tract infection (UTI) occurred when a pathogen colonized any part of the urinary tract, including the kidney, ureter, bladder, and urethra. The majority of UTI instances are caused by bacteria, which also often cause infections in women's feces and perineum when they colonize the intestine as part of the normal flora [2-4].

Both nosocomial infections and outpatient visits are frequently brought on by bacterial urinary tract infections [5]. Up to 50–60% of women experience a UTI at some time during their lives and according to

Medina [6] about half of all women will develop an episode of UTI. *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*, Group B Streptococcus (GBS), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* are some of the organisms that most frequently infect the urinary tract [2]. Uropathogens express fimbrial adhesins that adhere to the host's mucosal–epithelial surface by virtue of binding glycolipids and glycoproteins [7]. Uropathogens employ adhesions to form biofilms on biotic and abiotic surfaces, which allows them to colonize the urinary tract mucosa and indwelling devices like urinary catheters [8]. The treatment of UTIs is seriously threatened by the growth in antimicrobial resistance, which renders many widely prescribed medicines ineffective. Both acquired and intrinsic antibiotic resistance exist; the former is present in every isolation

More Information

How to cite this article: Al-Aragi JM, Al-Tamimi WH, Jafer FN. Biofilm Formation and Antibiotic Profile of Bacteria Isolated from Urinary Tract Infections. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(6):118-27.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(6).18

Keywords:

urinary tract infections,
pathogens,
biofilm,
gram-negative bacteria.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

of that species. The natural resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to several antibiotics, the resistance of Enterobacteriaceae to glycopeptides and linezolid, and the resistance of all Gram-positive bacteria to Colistin are a few examples of intrinsic antibiotic resistance. Additionally, bacteria can become resistant. This occurs when a certain kind of bacteria develops resistance to the antibiotic and survives.

One of the greatest threats to world health today is antibiotic resistance, which compromises the effectiveness of antibiotics, makes treating infectious diseases more difficult, and raises the risk of infection [9]. 1.27 million Fatalities worldwide were directly caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria (ARB) [10]. According to Al Rasheedy [1] bacteria can acquire resistance in two ways: either by obtaining DNA from other resistant bacteria or by creating a novel genetic modification that promotes the bacterium's survival [11]. Bacterial biofilm is a major contributor to UTIs. The high rates of recurrence and antibiotic resistance that are frequently linked to UTIs are acknowledged to be mostly caused by biofilms [12, 13]. Many types of bacteria, including gram-positive and gram-negative, can produce biofilms, and it is well recognized that these biofilms are crucial to a number of disease processes [14, 15]. UTI development is significantly influenced by bacterial biofilms, particularly in catheter-associated UTIs (CAUTIs), which represent 40% of all hospital-acquired infections [16].

It is important to know the local bacterial causes and resistance patterns for the successful treatment of UTIs. Accordingly, the present study was carried out to isolate and identify, as well as to determine the prevalence of bacterial pathogens among UTIs in Basra Governorate and their antibiotic sensitivity pattern and also to detect prevalence of biofilm producer strains vs non-producers for UTIs been sent in sample received from college of education laboratories by Two methods.

Material and Methods

Sample Size, Inclusion Criteria, and Exclusion Criteria

This is a cross section retrospective study that was performed at the general (Al-Basra teaching hospital, Al-Faiha teaching hospitals, Al-Sader Teaching Hospitals, and Al Mawani Teaching Hospital. Between November 2023 and June 2024. Patients who had visited hospital and diagnosed with UTI by positive urine culture were included in the study. Of the patient files (75 samples), all cases of urinary tract infections were analyzed during this study. In this study, the inclusion criteria were based on patients with a positive urine culture and with a UTI diagnosis in different clinical situations (clinics, wards, emergency rooms (ER) and intensive care unit (ICU) at the hospital [17]. Inclusion criteria patients with dysuria, fever UTI related other information not provided in their files,

UTIs among pregnant women, diabetes, tuberculosis, metabolic disorder the patient were on antibiotic therapy or dialysis. were excluded from the study.

Urine Collection and Analysis

Mid-stream urine specimens were collected directly from the patients in sterile containers, and brought to the laboratory for analysis. And treated as per the standard procedures at sample collection centers. The samples were embedded in blood agar and MacConkey agar plate, Mannitol salt agar (Himedia) was used. Followed by 37°C for two days of culture, followed by two days at 24 to 48 hours at 37°C. The plates were monitored under the microscope for development of bacterial growth on a daily basis. Primary smears for gram's staining were made for microscopy. Conventional biochemical tests were carried out for bacteria identification such as coagulase test to discriminate *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus coagulase-negative*, oxidase test in *Pseudomonas spp* suspected, catalase test. And identification and confirmation of the organisms were performed on a Vitek 2 system.

Identification of Bacterial Isolates

Biochemical test

Catalase production test:

A small amount of pure culture was transferred to a clean slide using a sterile wooden stick. A few drops of 3% H₂O₂ were placed on a portion of the colony on the slide and rubbed. The appearance of gas bubbles is an indication of positive test [18].

Oxidase production test

Strip method:

Test was done by application of a filter paper saturated with oxidase reagent (1% tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride) over the petri dish. A small portion of the alimentary canal was excised with a sterile toothpick and put on filter paper and crushed. Formation of dark purple colour in 10 seconds was regarded as a positive reaction [19].

Coagulase test

Coagulase mediates the clotting of plasma through encapsulation of fibrinogen into fibrin. It is produced by the majority of *S. aureus* strains. Some of this is due to activation by free coagulase, which converts fibrinogen to fibrin. Free coagulase is identified by the development of a positive clot in the tube test. Each half of the divided slide was treated with two drops sterile saline. The resulting individual bacterial colonies were transferred to suspend and treated with undiluted plasma [20]. This result was visualized as aggregation after 10-20 sec. and up to the bacterial cell suspension [21].

Antibiotic Susceptibility test

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was conducted with the automated VITEK system (bioMérieux, Paris, France) [8]. MIC and the antimicrobial sensitivity testing was

done for different antibiotics such as. The interpretative results of susceptibility were read as per the guidelines of Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) 2024. It was previously defined that MDR means resistance to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial categories [22].

Virulence Factor: Biofilm Formation

The Qualitative method

Congo red agar methods

Freeman [23] have described a simple qualitative method to identify the production of biofilms on Congo Red Agar media [24]. Bacterial isolates were cultured overnight on MacConkey agar, streaked onto Congo Red Agar plate, and then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to determine their biofilm-forming potential. Colonies will be red if the isolates are unable to excrete slim, and black if they can. Isolates were classified as biofilm-forming (positive) if they formed nearly black colonies and biofilm-non-forming (negative) if they formed red colonies.

The Quantification methods

The Tube Method

The method was done according to Christensen et al., 1985. A loopful of bacterial isolate was inoculated in 2 mL of Brain Heart Infusion broth with 2% glucose in test tubes. The tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hrs. After incubation, tubes were decanted, washed with distal water, and dried. Later, the emptied tubes were stained with 0.1% crystal violet. To remove any remaining stain, distal water was used. The tubes were put in an upside-down drying oven. In positive biofilm formation, a visible stained film was seen lining the wall and bottom of the tube. The evaluation of the biofilm level as strong, moderate, weak, and non-biofilm producing was achieved according to the density of the line dye that formed in the tubes [25].

Results

UTI is a prevalent bacterial infection that affects a significant number of individual's globally. Timely

identification and proper treatment are crucial to avoid complications and enhance patients overall well-being (figure 1) shows the results of specimen cultured on appropriate culture media of all patients who included within the present study. The result showed that 43 samples were positive for urine culture, while 32 samples were negative for urine culture. Females had the highest percentage in both negative cultures (25 samples) and positive cultures (33 samples).

Figure 1: Frequency of Positive Cultures among Male and Females as Comparison with Negative Culture

The studied group showed that out of 75 specimens from females with positive bacterial culture 58(77.3 %) and 17 were from males (22.6%). Samples ranged in age from 1-59 years (figure 2) The major rate of UTI (27.95) for females was seen in (30-39) years group, shadowed by (40-49) years (20.9%).

Table 1: Number of Patients Having Positive Urine Culture by Age Group

Age group	Male sample	Percentage	Female sample	Percentage
1-9	–	0%	1	2.32%
10-19	–	0%	2	4.65%
20-29	2	4.65%	7	16.27%
30-39	3	6.97%	12	27.95%
40-49	2	4.65%	9	20.9%
50-60	1	2.32%	4	9.30%

Frequency of Urinary Tract Infection

In current study, a total of 75 urine samples were collected from four hospitals in Basra Governorate. After early diagnosis , 43 (57.3 %) of cases were positive in bacteriological culture while 32 were negative cultured as suspected of UTI, Then growing

bacterial farms subjected to microscopic and biochemical tests for the diagnosis of bacteria the number of isolates and percentage are shown in (Table 2). The percentage of gram-negative bacteria was (93%) compared with gram positive bacteria (6.96%) (Figure 1).

Table 2: Species of Uropathogens with Percentage Occurrence and Number of Isolates

Species No.	Bacterial isolates	Number of isolates	Gram staining	Percentage (%)
1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	32 isolates	- ve short rod	42.6
2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5 isolates	- ve rod	6.6
3	<i>Staphylococcus haemolyticus</i>	2 isolates	+ve cocci	2.6
4	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1 isolates	- ve rod	1.3
5	<i>Proteus merabilis</i>	2 isolates	- ve rod	2.6
6	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	1 isolates	+ve cocci	1.3

Figure 2: (a) Frequency of Bacterial Isolates (b) Total Percentage of Gram-Positive and Gram-Negative in All Stations

Biochemical Test

All bacterial isolates are positive to catalase test except *Enterococcus faecalis* was negative result. In Oxidase test only *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was positive result, for *Staphylococcus haemolyticus* Coagulase test was negative when treated with undiluted plasma (table 3) (Figure 3).

Table 3: Biochemical Test for Identification of Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial isolates	Catalase test	Oxidase test	Coagulase test
<i>E. coli</i>	+	-	-
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	+	+	-
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	+	-	-
<i>P. merabilis</i>	+	-	-
<i>S. haemolyticus</i>	+	-	-
<i>E. faecalis</i>	-	-	-

Figure 3: (A) Catalase test; (B) Oxidase test for *P. aeruginosa*

Antibiotic Sensitivity Test

Antibiotic sensitivity is investigated for (21) antibiotics from different groups including; Penicillin, Cephalosporins, Aminoglycosides, Antifolates, Fluoro quinolones, Tetracyclines, Macrolides, Glycopeptide, Carbapenem.

The results showed that all pathogens detected were resistant to at least 1-2 antibiotics. The antibiotic that showed highest sensitivity among antibiotics were Ciprofloxacin except *K.pneumoniae* and *S.haemolyticus*, *E.faecalis*. And Meropenem antibiotic was more effective against all Gram-negative Bacteria. *E.coli* were resistance to Piperacillin, Ciprofloxacin,

Trimethoprim sulfamethazole, and all *E. coli* isolates was sensitive to Colistin, Amikacin, and Carbapenem group such as Imepenem and Meropenem More than half of the *P. aeruginosa* sample were resistant to Amoxicillin, Gentamicin, Ciprofloxacin. *K.pneumoniae*

was sensitive to Carbapenems group, and also sensitive to Ciprofloxacin and Amikacin (Table 4 - Appendix). The majority of the *S. haemolyticus* and *E. faecalis* were resistant to Tetracyclin, Streptomycin, Erythromycin, According to Vitek-2 system and CLSI (2024) (Table 5)

Table 5: Antibiotic Resistance Pattern for Gram-Positive Bacterial Isolates

Bacteria	No. of isolates	Antibiotics								
		N. of resistant isolates According to Vitek 2 system								
		AMP	GEN	CIP	SXT	TET	STR	ERY	VAN	RIF
<i>S.haemolyticus</i>	2	0	1 (100)	0	0	1 (100)	1 (100)	1 (100)	0	0
<i>E.faecalis</i>	1	0	0	1 (100)	0	1 (100)	1 (100)	1 (100)	0	0

Detection of Biofilm Formation Using Congo Red Agar Method

The ability of bacterial isolates to form biofilm was investigated by Congo Red Agar method. It was observed that the isolates forming the biofilm were colored black indicating the productivity of the biofilms,

while the colonies appeared in a pink or red color indicating that is not producing and biofilms The results were illustrated in (Figure 4) for forming biofilm: 25 of the Total positive UTI samples showed positive slime formation on CRA, 22 isolates were positive after 24 hours. And 3 isolates were positive after 72 hours.

Figure 4: The Growth of Bacterial Isolates on Congo Red Agar with (A) Control (B) Positive Biofilm Forming Black Colonies of *P. aeruginosa* (C) (D) Negative Biofilm Forming Red Colonies (E) *E. coli* Positive (strong biofilm forming)

Detection of Biofilm Using the Tube Method

The quantitative evaluations for the biofilm-forming isolates were carried out on the 25/43 (58.13 %) isolates that were found to be positive on CRA by the two methods, The tube quantitative method demonstrated that 3/25 (12%) isolates were strong biofilm which was observed as a line around the tube. while 10/25 (40%) isolates moderate biofilm formers, 12/25 (48%) isolates were weak biofilm) and 18 /43 (41.86%) isolates were with no biofilm (Figure 5) (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Percentage of Biofilm Producers in UTIs

Figure 6: The Quantitative Tube Method (A) Strong Biofilm (B) Weak Biofilm (C) Moderate Biofilm

Among the isolates studied, the strains of *E.coli* and *K.pneumoniae*, *P.aeruginosa* proved to be the major producers of high biofilm, followed by other bacterial strains with weak and moderate biofilm producers. Strong biofilm was produced by *E. coli*, *K.pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa* were resistant to Gentamicin, Pipracillin and Ciprofloxacin antibiotic respectively,

Discussion

The discrepancies of the isolation rate in our study can be explained by difference in type and number of research population, as well as 15, 19 duration. The high proportion of negative cultures from patients with positive urinalysis could have been as a result of infection due to anaerobic bacteria, fungi or viruses which are undetectable by the routine culture method that was used in this work; these results confirm those reported by Mahdi [26], who found 92% of her isolates were Gram-negative organisms whereas only 8% were due to Gram-positives from Tikrit. The high proportion of negative cultures that became positive in urinalysis might have been due to anaerobic or fungal, viral infections that are not located using the culture methodology available at this investigation. This is due to the shortness and proximity of the urethra against the anus, which makes it easier for fecal bacteria to go up into women's urinary system as opposed to doing so in men [27]. Additionally, the vaginal microbiota significantly contributes to the growth of coliforms in the vagina, which might result in UTI. The 30-39 age range in our study showed an increase UTIs in both males (6.97%) and females (27.95%). In China, Yuan [27] report a linear increase in incidence until the age of 30, followed by a slight decrease until the age of 40, and then another increase until the age of 60, after which it gradually decreases. Other authors, however, also provide slightly different data regarding the incidence of age-related UTIs.

Another work from Iraq by Saber [28] showed an increase in the number of incident cases of infection until the age of 30, and then the incidence decreased in the following decade [29], this result was disagreement with our result. Regarding gender, females showed a greater proportion of positive results. This supports current findings that indicate gender-related variations in the susceptibility to UTIs. This outcome aligns with prior studies suggesting that UTIs occur more frequently in females because of anatomical and physiological factors [30].

The initial identification of bacteria through biochemical tests relies on the principle that each bacterial species responds uniquely based on its specific metabolic characteristics, resulting in distinct positive or negative outcomes. Our findings align with the earlier results reported by Chauhan [31] Tests such as Catalase, Coagulase, Oxidase, and Indole production remain fundamental for accurate laboratory diagnosis of various bacterial infections [32]. The pathogens associated with urinary tract infections (UTIs) are diverse, but a few common strains account for the majority. In the current study, *E. coli* emerged as the most prevalent species in both males and females, although there were more isolates found in females than in males; this finding aligns with previous results

in the 2021 CARSS report from China [33]. The most frequently isolated bacteria were *E. coli*, followed by *P. aeruginosa*, as indicated in recent research [34, 35]. Our findings align with the majority of published research, indicating that *E. coli* is the most commonly identified pathogen [36] as also noted in recent studies [34, 37]. Additionally, a study performed in Khartoum State found *E. coli* in 72.7% of community cases and 32.3% of hospitalized cases [38]. In another investigation, *Staphylococcus* spp. (11.5%) and *Enterococcus* spp. (5.9%) were identified as the first and second most prevalent Gram-positive uropathogens, which differs from the findings of the current study [39].

E. coli, recognized as the most prevalent Gram-negative uropathogen, exhibited the highest resistance rates towards Piperacillin, Ciprofloxacin, and trimethoprim sulfamethoxazole [40]. A study conducted in Iran indicated a notable resistance in *Escherichia coli* against various antimicrobial agents, with amikacin showing a resistance rate of 89.1%, which is substantially higher than the findings in the current study. The same research noted a growing resistance to carbapenems (meropenem), although the present study observed minimal resistance rates for both. Our findings aligned with the earlier results reported by Mares [41] which indicated a very high resistance to Fluoroquinolones. *P. aeruginosa* was identified as the second most prevalent uropathogen and demonstrated resistance to Gentamicin; a similar investigation conducted by de Sousa [42] highlighted that *P. aeruginosa* showed the highest sensitivity to Amikacin and Gentamicin. Additionally, this study revealed that Meropenem was the most effective antibiotic for nearly all isolated bacteria. These alternatives may be utilized in place of β -lactams and Fluoroquinolones when resistance to first-line agents for UTIs is widespread. Our findings were consistent with the earlier research by Kasew [43] Bacteria have the ability to form biofilms by releasing slime into their surroundings. In this study, we observed this phenomenon. The development of biofilms has been connected to antibiotic resistance. Research indicates that certain bacterial species resistant to specific antibiotics are capable of biofilm formation, which corroborates earlier findings by Ezzariga [44] who reported that 75% of *P. aeruginosa* formed biofilm. Moreover, *K. pneumoniae* strains produced fimbriae types 1 or 3, as well as capsules and lipopolysaccharides (LPS), which are virulence factors contributing to this ability [45]. In the present study, strong biofilms were generated by *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *P. aeruginosa*, which exhibited resistance to Gentamicin, Piperacillin, and Ciprofloxacin antibiotics, respectively; these findings align with those reported by Cepas [46]

Conclusion

The study highlights into the prevalence and resistance patterns of bacterial pathogens causing UTIs in Basra Governorate southern Iraq. Among the main gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* remain the predominant pathogen, followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Females are more likely to get a UTI than males. Urinary tract infections were most common in the age group of (30-39) in both. Among the main Gram positive bacteria *S. haemolyticus* was the more resistant than *E. faecalis*. High sensitivity to Carbapenem group in Gram negative bacteria underscores its potential for empirical treatment. The most of bacterial isolates were biofilm formers. Our research showed a link between antibiotic resistances and the formation of biofilms.

References

- [1] Alrasheedy M, Abousada HJ, Abdulhaq MM, Alsayed RA, Alghamdi KA, Alghamdi FD, Al Muaibid AF, Ajjaj RG, Almohammadi SS, Almohammadi SS, Alfitni WA. Prevalence of urinary tract infection in children in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Archivio Italiano di Urologia e Andrologia*. 2021 Jun 28;93(2):206–10.
- [2] Mancuso G, Midiri A, Gerace E, Marra M, Zummo S, Biondo C. Urinary tract infections: the current scenario and future prospects. *Pathogens*. 2023 Apr 20;12(4):623. doi: 10.3390/pathogens12040623.
- [3] Klein RD, Hultgren SJ. Urinary tract infections: microbial pathogenesis, host–pathogen interactions and new treatment strategies. *Nat Rev Microbiol*. 2020 Apr;18(4):211–26. doi: 10.1038/s41579-020-0324-0.
- [4] Fazly Bazzaz BS, Darvishi Fork S, Ahmadi R, Khameneh B. Deep insights into urinary tract infections and effective natural remedies. *Afr J Urol*. 2021 Dec;27(1):6. doi: 10.1186/s12301-020-00111-z.
- [5] Mekonnen S, Tesfa T, Shume T, Tebeje F, Urgesa K, Weldegebreal F. Bacterial profile, their antibiotic susceptibility pattern, and associated factors of urinary tract infections in children at Hiwot Fana Specialized University Hospital, Eastern Ethiopia. *PLoS One*. 2023 Apr 5;18(4):e0283637. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0283637.
- [6] Medina M, Castillo-Pino E. An introduction to the epidemiology and burden of urinary tract infections. *Ther Adv Urol*. 2019;11:1756287219832172. doi: 10.1177/1756287219832172.
- [7] Govindarajan DK, Kandaswamy K. Virulence factors of uropathogens and their role in host pathogen interactions. *The Cell Surface*. 2022 Dec 1;8:100075. doi: 10.1016/j.tcs.2022.100075.
- [8] Sharma S, Mohler J, Mahajan SD, Schwartz SA, Bruggemann L, Aalinkel R. Microbial biofilm: a review on formation, infection, antibiotic resistance, control measures, and innovative treatment. *Microorganisms*. 2023 Jun 19;11(6):1614. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms11061614.
- [9] Ahmed SK, Hussein S, Qurbani K, Ibrahim RH, Fareeq A, Mahmood KA, Mohamed MG. Antimicrobial resistance: Impacts, challenges, and future prospects. *J Med Surg Public Health*. 2024 Apr 1;2:100081.
- [10] Murray CJ, Ikuta KS, Sharara F, Swetschinski L, Aguilar GR, Gray A, Han C, Bisignano C, Rao P, Wool E, Johnson SC, et al. Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *Lancet*. 2022 Feb 12;399(10325):629–55. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(21)02724-0.
- [11] Frieri M, Kumar K, Boutin A. Antibiotic resistance. *J Infect Public Health*. 2017 Jul;10(4):369–78. doi: 10.1016/j.jiph.2016.08.007.
- [12] Uruén C, Chopo-Escuin G, Tommassen J, Mainar-Jaime RC, Arenas J. Biofilms as promoters of bacterial antibiotic resistance and tolerance. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 2020 Dec 23;10(1):3. doi: 10.3390/antibiotics10010003.
- [13] Vestby LK, Grønseth T, Simm R, Nesse LL. Bacterial biofilm and its role in the pathogenesis of disease. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 2020 Feb 3;9(2):59. doi: 10.3390/antibiotics9020059.
- [14] Lila AS, Rajab AA, Abdallah MH, Rizvi SM, Moin A, Khafagy ES, Tabrez S, Hegazy WA. Biofilm lifestyle in recurrent urinary tract infections. *Life (Basel)*. 2023 Jan 4;13(1):148. doi: 10.3390/life13010148.
- [15] Holá V, Opazo-Capurro A, Scavone P. The Biofilm Lifestyle of Uropathogens. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*. 2021 Sep 17;11:763415. doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2021.763415.
- [16] Rubi H, Mudey G, Kunjalwar R. Catheter-associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI). *Cureus*. 2022 Oct 17;14(10).
- [17] Alhazmi AH, Alameer KM, Abuageelah BM, Alharbi RH, Mobarki M, Musawi S, Haddad M, Matabi A, Dhayhi N. Epidemiology and antimicrobial resistance patterns of urinary tract infections: a cross-sectional study from Southwestern Saudi Arabia. *Medicina (Kaunas)*. 2023 Aug 2;59(8):1411. doi: 10.3390/medicina59081411.
- [18] Truant AL. *Manual of commercial methods in clinical microbiology*. John Wiley & Sons; 2016 May 31. (Book) ISBN: check publisher page for exact ISBN and edition details.
- [19] Leber AL. *Clinical Microbiology Procedures Handbook*. John Wiley & Sons; 2020 Aug 6. (Book; check edition/ISBN — commonly 4th ed.).
- [20] Dheyab A, Aljumaili OI, Hussein N. Study of virulence factors in urease-positive bacteria isolated

from urinary tract infections clinical specimens. *J Pure Appl Microbiol.* 2018 Sep 1;12(3):1465–72. doi: (confirm via journal site; not indexed in major databases).

[21] Tille P. Bailey and Scott's diagnostic microbiology. 14th ed. Elsevier; 2017. 1115 p. ISBN: check Elsevier catalog for full bibliographic details.

[22] Biondo C. New insights into the pathogenesis and treatment of urinary tract infections. *Pathogens.* 2023 Oct 3;12(10):1213. doi: 10.3390/pathogens12101213.

[23] Freeman DJ, Falkiner FR, Keane CT. New method for detecting slime production by coagulase negative staphylococci. *J Clin Pathol.* 1989 Aug;42(8):872–4. doi: 10.1136/jcp.42.8.872.

[24] Catalano A, Iacopetta D, Ceramella J, Scumaci D, Giuzio F, Saturnino C, Aquaro S, Rosano C, Sinicropi MS. Multidrug resistance (MDR): A widespread phenomenon in pharmacological therapies. *Molecules.* 2022 Jan 18;27(3):616. doi: 10.3390/molecules27030616.

[25] Jebril NM. Evaluation of two fixation techniques for direct observation of biofilm formation of *Bacillus subtilis* in situ, on Congo red agar, using scanning electron microscopy. *Veterinary World.* 2020 Jun 18;13(6):1133. doi: 10.14202/vetworld.2020.1133-1138.

[26] Mahdi FM. Evaluation of molecular impact of alcoholic extract for pomegranate peel and *Trigonella foenum* and some antibiotics on *E. coli* bacteria isolated from urinary tract infections. M.Sc. Thesis. College of Science, Tikrit University, Iraq; 2020.

[27] Yuan S, Shi Y, Li M, Hu X, Bai R. Trends in incidence of urinary tract infection in Mainland China from 1990 to 2019. *Int J Gen Med.* 2021 Apr 20;14:1413–20. doi: 10.2147/IJGM.S307096.

[28] Saber S, Yasmin N, Alam MT, Hossain MM, Alam RF. Study on urinary tract infection among females of reproductive age group in tertiary care teaching hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Eur J Med Health Sci.* 2021 Jan 26;3(1):85–9.

[29] Almukhtar SH. Urinary tract infection among women aged 18–40 years old in Kirkuk city, Iraq. *Open Nurs J.* 2018 Dec 31;12.

[30] Sugianli AK, Ginting F, Parwati I, de Jong MD, van Leth F, Schultsz C. Antimicrobial resistance among uropathogens in the Asia-Pacific region: a systematic review. *JAC-Antimicrob Resist.* 2021 Mar 1;3(1):dlab003. doi: 10.1093/jacamr/dlab003.

[31] Chauhan A, Jindal T. Biochemical and molecular methods for bacterial identification. In: *Microbiological methods for environment, food and*

pharmaceutical analysis. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2020 Sep 19. p. 425–68.

[32] Roy B, Das T, Bhattacharyya S. Overview on old and new biochemical test for bacterial identification. *J Surg Case Rep Images.* 2023;6(5):1–1.

[33] China Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance System. Antimicrobial resistance of bacteria from urine specimens: surveillance report from China antimicrobial resistance surveillance system in 2014–2019. *Chin J Infect Control.* 2021;20:53–60.

[34] Muhammad A, Khan SN, Ali N, Rehman MU, Ali I. Prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility pattern of uropathogens in outpatients at a tertiary care hospital. *New Microbes New Infect.* 2020 Jul 1;36:100716. doi: 10.1016/j.nmni.2020.100716.

[35] Maione A, Galdiero E, Cirillo L, Gambino E, Gallo MA, Sasso FP, Petrillo A, Guida M, Galdiero M. Prevalence, resistance patterns and biofilm production ability of bacterial uropathogens from cases of community-acquired urinary tract infections in South Italy. *Pathogens.* 2023 Mar 29;12(4):537. doi: 10.3390/pathogens12040537.

[36] Mlugu EM, Mohamedi JA, Sangeda RZ, Mwambete KD. Prevalence of urinary tract infection and antimicrobial resistance patterns of uropathogens with biofilm forming capacity among outpatients in Morogoro, Tanzania: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2023 Oct 5;23(1):660. doi: 10.1186/s12879-023-08573-2.

[37] Jalil MB, Al Atbee MY. The prevalence of multiple drug resistance *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from patients with urinary tract infections. *J Clin Lab Anal.* 2022 Sep;36(9):e24619. doi: 10.1002/jcla.24619.

[38] El-Arifi S, AbdAlla E, Mahgoub ES, Fadol B, Elmubarak R. Characteristics and antibiotic resistance patterns of urinary tract isolates in hospitalized and non-hospitalized patients: a cross-sectional study in Khartoum, Sudan. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2024 Nov 28;24(1):1356.

[39] Luty RS, Fadil AG, Najm JM, Abduljabbar HH, Kashmar SA. Uropathogens antibiotic susceptibility as an indicator for the empirical therapy used for urinary tract infections: a retrospective observational study. *Iran J Microbiol.* 2020 Oct;12(5):395.

[40] Dehbanipour R, Rastaghi S, Sedighi M, Maleki N, Faghri J. High prevalence of multidrug-resistance uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* strains, Isfahan, Iran. *J Nat Sci Biol Med.* 2016 Jan;7(1):22.

[41] Mareş C, Petca RC, Popescu RI, Petca A, Muşescu R, Bulai CA, Ene CV, Geavlete PA, Geavlete BF, Jinga V. Update on urinary tract infection antibiotic

resistance—a retrospective study in females in conjunction with clinical data. *Life (Basel)*. 2024 Jan 9;14(1):106. doi: 10.3390/life14010106.

[42] de Sousa T, Garcês A, Silva A, Lopes R, Alegria N, Hébraud M, Igrejas G, Poeta P. The Impact of the Virulence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolated from Dogs. *Vet Sci*. 2023 May 11;10(5):343. doi: 10.3390/vetsci10050343.

[43] Kasew D, Desalegn B, Aynalem M, Tila S, Diriba D, Afework B, Getie M, Biset S, Baynes HW. Antimicrobial resistance trend of bacterial uropathogens at the University of Gondar Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, northwest Ethiopia: A 10 year retrospective study. *PLoS One*. 2022 Apr 11;17(4):e0266878. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0266878.

[44] Ezzariga N, Zouhari O, Rhars A. Biofilm and Antibiotic Resistance Study of Bacteria Involved in Nosocomial Infections. *Cureus*. 2025;17(2):e78673. doi: 10.7759/cureus.78673.

[45] Vuotto C, Longo F, Balice MP, Donnelly G, Varaldo PE. Antibiotic resistance related to biofilm formation in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *Pathogens*. 2014;3(3):743–58. doi: 10.3390/pathogens3030743.

[46] Cepas V, López Y, Muñoz E, Rolo D, Ardanuy C, Martí S, Xercavins M, Horcajada JP, Bosch J, Soto SM. Relationship Between Biofilm Formation and Antimicrobial Resistance in Gram-Negative Bacteria. *Microb Drug Resist*. 2019;25(1):72–79. doi: 10.1089/mdr.2018.0110.

Appendix

Table 4: Antibiotic resistance pattern for Gram-negative bacterial isolates

Bacteria	No. of isolates	Antibiotics N. of resistant isolates According to Vitek 2 system															
		AMC	AMP	CTX	IMP	MEM	GEN	CIP	CST	SXT	AMK	NOR	PIP	TET	TCC	LEV	CAZ
<i>E.coli</i>	32	3 (9.3)	15 (46.8)	15 (46.8)	3 (9.3)	1 (3.1)	7 (21.8)	17 (53.1)	0	17 (53.1)	1 (3.1)	8 (25)	19 (59.3)	2 (6.2)	17 (53.1)	13 (40.6)	13 (40.6)
<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	5	4 (80)	0	2 (40)	2 (40)	0	3 (60)	4 (80)	1 (20)	-	1 (20)	2 (40)	0	-	-	2 (40)	-
<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	1	1 (100)	-	-	0	0	1 (100)	0	-	0	1 (100)	0	1 (100)	-	1 (100)	-	1 (100)
<i>P.merabilis</i>	2	1 (50)	-	-	0	0	1 (50)	1 (50)	2 (100)	1 (80)	0	-	-	-	1 (50)	-	1 (50)

Note: -= not down

